

STUDY OF PRECAST STEEL FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE WALL-COLUMN CONNECTION WITH OPENING

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates precast steel fibre reinforced concrete (SFRC) wall-column connections with openings under blast loading, crucial for enhancing structural resilience against terrorist threats. The research focuses on improving the connection's integrity using steel fibres and headed bars. It begins with an analysis of blast effects on structures, emphasizing the need for enhanced blast protection measures. Concrete, precast elements, SFRC, and headed bars are discussed to provide a foundation for the study. Objectives include analyzing the behaviour of precast SFRC systems, studying the effect of steel fibres, and assessing headed bar connections. Finite element analysis in ANSYS Workbench models various connection configurations, showing deformations, stresses, and strains. Results show effective modelling and suggest steel fibres and headed bars enhance blast resistance in precast structures.

Keywords: Blast loading, precast concrete, steel fiber reinforced concrete, headed bars, finite element analysis, structural resilience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Terrorist threats and deeds are becoming a more common problem these days. Thus, it is found that the concept of blast protection is essential to structural engineers' job. In constructing structures, it is important to take into account blast load as well as other dynamic loads like earthquake and wind loads since there have been an increasing number of terrorist attacks in recent years, especially in big cities. Attacks by terrorists usually target places where there is a high chance of serious human losses as well as economic consequences. Because structural structures are easily accessible and may have an impact on both economic activity and human lives, targets are said to be attracted to them. Although the wall helps to bear lateral pressures and then shifts the weight to the foundation, the main objective of the research is to strengthen the precast reinforced concrete wall-column connection with steel fibres and headed bars in order to sustain the blast load. The frequency of terrorist attacks throughout the globe is rising, and structural designers are finding that blast protection strategies are an important consideration. Because they are often not designed to sustain blast loads and have design loads that are far lower than those produced by the bulk of explosions, conventional structures are susceptible to explosion damage. There was no civil building that could withstand the kind of heavy attack that brought down the World Trade Centre in the United States. But in an uncertain environment, building owners and designers need to be proactive in identifying potential threats and protecting occupants and property. Developers, architects, and engineers are searching more and more for ways to prevent potential explosive situations in order to protect building occupants as well as the structures. In order to circumvent this, steel fibres are the most often used kind of reinforcement in concrete because of their high tensile strength. Additional joint or connection technologies, such as headed bars, are used to enhance the structure's flexibility.

1.1 PRECAST CONCRETE

Precast concrete is a construction product produced by casting concrete in a reusable mold or "form" which is then cured in a controlled environment, transported to the construction site and lifted into place. In contrast, standard concrete is poured into site-specific forms and cured on site. This is lightweight and has better thermal insulation. Precast is used within exterior and interior walls. By producing precast concrete in a controlled environment (typically referred to as a precast plant), the precast concrete is afforded the opportunity to properly cure and be closely monitored by plant employees. Using a precast concrete system offers many potential advantages over onsite casting. Precast concrete production can be performed on ground level, which helps with safety throughout a project. There is greater control over material quality and workmanship in a precast plant compared to a construction site. The forms used in a precast plant can be reused hundreds to thousands of times before they have to be replaced, often making it cheaper than onsite casting when looking at the cost per unit of formwork.

1.2 STEEL FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE

Fibres reinforced concrete is a composite material comprised of Portland cement, aggregate, and fibers. Normal unreinforced concrete is brittle with a low tensile strength and strain capacity. The function of the irregular fibers distributed randomly is to fill the cracks in the composite.

Steel fibre reinforced concrete is a composite material having fibers as the additional ingredients, dispersed uniformly at random in small percentages, i.e. between 0.3% and 2.5% by volume in plain concrete.

There are different types of steel fibers such as straight steel fibers, Crimped Steel Fibres and Hooked Steel Fibres of which hooked steel fibers are mostly used because of its stronger pull-out resistance than the other types of fibers which reduces the cracking in concrete.

Figure 1. Hooked Steel Fibers

II. Literature review

A review of the literature is an analysis of a particular topic using scholarly sources. With the help of its summary of scientific data, you may identify relevant research ideas, procedures, and gaps. The literature review for this study is as follows:

Russell P. Burrell, Hassan Aoude, and Murat Saatcioglu The study aimed to evaluate the performance of steel fiber-reinforced concrete columns under simulated blast loading. To do this, four half-scale column specimens were built using self-consolidating concrete and reinforced with steel fibre at varying percentages of 0% to 1.5% by concrete volume. Using the University of Ottawa's cutting-edge shock-tube testing equipment, half-scale columns were built and subjected to various simulated blast pressure–impulse combinations. According to the current research, using SFRC improved the blast performance of columns in terms of maximum and residual displacements, flexural capacity, shear capacity, and damage tolerance. Traditional reinforced concrete columns subjected to blast loading were found to be deficient in flexural capacity, concrete confinement, and shear capacity. It was also determined that better blast performance was achieved when seismic details was included in column design.

Sana N. Kazi, P. V. Muley Analysis of blast resistant RCC structure”

This work examines the impact of blast loads on a six-story reinforced concrete structure. The impact of varying blast source weight was computed by taking into account a distance of 30 metres from the explosion site. Using a pressure-time history and a numerical model of the structure made in SAP2000, the blast load was calculated analytically. Calculations and comparisons were made on the impact of the blast-related lateral load response on peak deflections, velocity, accelerations, and inter-story drift. The building's core node saw the most displacement. Additionally, the top story was determined to have the largest displacement. The top storey of columns and beams saw the highest shear forces and moments as the distance from the explosion source grew, whereas the axial forces in columns peaked at the first story.

Duc-Kien Thai, Seung-Eock Kim Numerical investigation of the damage of RC members subjected to blast loading”

A numerical analysis of the damage caused by blast loading on reinforced concrete (RC) columns is presented in this work. LS-DYNA is used in the development and analysis of a dependable finite element (FE) model of an RC member's blast test. The blast test data provided in the most current works is then used to validate the FE models. Analysis is done on six sets of RC columns with square sections that are 250 mm by 250 mm, 500 mm by 500 mm, and 800 mm by 800 mm, and all have the same free height of 3.6 m. These columns are exposed to explosions with various standoff distances. The analysis's findings indicate that although the thin columns exhibit both local and global damage, the "stocky" columns—that is, columns with substantial dimensions—only show local damage. Furthermore, a significant factor in the column's damage is the charge location. When an explosion is charged at the mid-height of an RC column, it results in more substantial damage than when it is charged at the base. This study found that when a blast load is applied, the size of the column and the charge location both matter.

Omar Algassem, Yang Li, Hassan Aoude Ability of steel fibers to enhance the shear and flexural behavior of high strength concrete beams subjected to blast loads”

The findings of an experimental programme investigating the impact of steel fibres on the blast performance of high-strength concrete beams are presented in this work. Ten HSFRC beams are tested as part of the investigation, either with static loads or with simulated blast loads using a shock-tube. The impacts of fibres, fibre type, fibre quantity, longitudinal steel ratio, and the combination of fibre and transverse reinforcement are among the test factors. The findings demonstrate that adding fibres to HSC beams improves damage tolerance, enhances blast resistance, and controls displacements better. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that 1% of steel fibres may serve as a stand-in for transverse reinforcement and stop blast-related shear failures. Additionally, it was shown that short fibres work better than long fibres to reduce blast-induced deformation when used in conjunction with transverse reinforcement and steel fibre. The analytical examination demonstrates that the blast response of HSFRC beams may be accurately predicted by using SDOF analysis in conjunction with the construction of non-linear resistance functions.

Jean Paul Vella, Robert L. Vollum, “An drew Jackson Flexural Behaviour of Headed Bar Connections Between Precast Concrete Panels”

The study details a set of flexural tests performed on specimens made up of two precast element pairs joined by 25 mm diameter overlapping headed bars. Within a 200 mm wide in situ concrete joint, where transverse bars and vertical shear studs were inserted to provide confinement, the headed bars overlapped by 100 mm. Because of off-site manufacturing, this kind of connection makes it easier to manufacture continuously reinforced slabs from precast pieces, which leads to considerable savings in total construction time and increases in construction quality. The impact of confining shear studs, out-of-plane offset of precast planks, and concrete strength on joint strength, ductility, and crack breadth was examined in the experiments. Joint concrete with a cylinder compressive strength of 39 MPa was able to accomplish ductile failure with a yield of 25 mm diameter high strength headed bars. Joint concrete strength is primarily responsible for determining flexural strength and stiffness. A nonlinear finite element model is proposed, which sheds light on joint behaviour and makes accurate predictions about joint strength.

Xiaoshan Lin, Y.X. Zhang, Paul J. Hazell Modelling the response of reinforced concrete panels under blast loading”

In order to predict the structural reaction of steel-reinforced concrete panels under blast loading, a finite element model is constructed in LS-DYNA in this article. The impact of element size is examined, and the finite element model takes into account the independent impacts of strain-rate on the compressive and tensile strengths of the concrete. The efficacy and accuracy of the proposed finite element model for predicting reinforced concrete panels under blast loading are presented, and it has been confirmed using several experimental data from the literature. The parametric investigation demonstrates that the explosion response of reinforced concrete panels is significantly influenced by the explosive charge's mass and the standoff distance. As might be predicted, the stand-off distance and charge mass selection have a significant impact on the maximum displacement at the panel's centre. Furthermore, it has been shown that by raising the panel's thickness and reinforcement ratio, the deflection of reinforced concrete panels may also be decreased.

“Wasim Abbass, M. Iqbal Khan, Shehab Mourad Evaluation of Mechanical Properties of Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete with Different Strengths of Concrete”

This research examines how adding steel fibres to concrete at three different concrete strength levels affects the mechanical characteristics of the material. Three lengths (40, 50, and 60 mm) and two diameters (0.62 and 0.75 mm) of hooked-ended fibres were used in this investigation, along with three water-to-cement ratios (0.25, 0.35, and 0.45). Three volume fractions of steel fibers—0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5%—were added. Thirty different concrete mixtures were made and examined. The findings showed that adding steel fibres of varying lengths and contents to concrete at increasing water-to-cement ratios significantly altered the concrete's mechanical characteristics, boosting its direct tensile strength by around 31-47% and its compressive strength by about 10-25%. For fibre with a lower aspect ratio of 65, increasing the fibre content from 0.5% to 1.5% resulted in a flexural strength increase from 3% to 124%; whereas, for fibre with a larger aspect ratio of 80, a 140% increase in flexural strength was seen in comparison to the concrete without any fibres. An analytical model is provided to analyse the stress-strain relationship of fiber-reinforced concrete under compression, taking into account steel fibres with varying lengths and diameters.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for studying precast steel fibre reinforced concrete (SFRC) wall-column connections with openings using the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) method involves several key steps. Initially, detailed geometric models of the wall-column connections, both with and without circular openings, are created using CAD software. Material properties for SFRC, including tensile strength, compressive strength, and fibre characteristics, are accurately defined. The models are then imported into an FEA software, where boundary conditions and load cases, including blast loading scenarios, are applied. Meshing is performed to ensure computational accuracy, followed by the simulation of structural responses. The results, such as deformation, stress distribution, and strain, are analyzed to assess the impact of openings on the structural performance.

3.1 Materials Properties.

The characteristics of the “A3” beam and the real properties of materials are presented in Table 1. It is noteworthy citing that this observes additionally taken into consideration other configurations for the connectors, as number, height and diameter. Materials properties of composite beam were as follows

Table 1. Material properties

Sr. No.	Material	Property	Value
1	Structural steel	Yield stress f_{sy} (MPa)	265
		Ultimate strength f_{su} (MPa)	410
		Young's modulus E_s (MPa)	205
		Poisson's ratio μ	0.3
		Ultimate tensile strain e_t	0.25
2	Reinforcing bar	Yield stress f_{sy} (MPa)	250
		Ultimate strength f_{su} (MPa)	350
		Young's modulus E_s (MPa)	200
		Poisson's ratio μ	0.3
		Ultimate tensile strain e_t	0.25
3	Concrete	Compressive strength f_{sc} (MPa)	42.5
		Tensile strength f_{sy} (MPa)	3.553
		Young's modulus E_c (MPa)	32920
		Poisson's ratio μ	0.15
		Ultimate compressive strain e_s	0.045
4	Stud shear connector	Spacing (mm)	110
		Number of rows	2
		Numbers of connectors	68
		Yield stress f_{sy} (MPa)	435
		Ultimate strength f_{su} (MPa)	565
		Young's modulus E_s (MPa)	200
		Poisson's ratio μ	0.15
Ultimate strain e	0.045		

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND MODELING

The terrorist activities and threats have become a growing problem all over the world and protection of the citizens against terrorist acts involves prediction, prevention and mitigation of such events. In the case of structures an effective mitigation may also be thought in the terms of structural resistance and physical integrity. Analysis of precast reinforced concrete wall-column system subjected to blast loading using ANSYS WORKBENCH Software. Precast RC wall-column system considered here consists of a 2260 mm high, 150 mm thick solid wall connected to 350 × 350 mm precast RC hollow columns and M30 concrete and Fe415 steel. the circular opening diameter 160mm.

Carry out a comparative study of precast reinforced concrete wall-column system using dowel bars and headed bars as connection system with and without steel fibres.

Fig. 4. Precast RC wall and columns connected through

Modelling Geometry

Figure 5. Geometry of Wall Without Opening and with opening

Total deformation

Figure 6.Total deformation

The figure show total defrmnt of wall without opening is 26.099 mm and wall with opening 24.455 mm

Equivalent Stress

Figure 7. Equivalent Stress

The figure show Equivalent Stress of wall without opening is 116.32Mpa and wall with opening 107.44Mpa.

Normal Stress

Figure 8. Normal Stress

The figure show Normal Stress of wall without opening is 16.031Mpa and wall with opening 14.76 Mpa.

Equivalent elastic Strain

Figure 9. Equivalent elastic Strain

The figure show Equivalent elastic Strain of wall without opening is 0.0033 and wall with opening 0.0030.

Shear Stress

Figure 10 Shear Stress

The figure show Normal Stress of wall without opening is 20.039Mpa and wall with opening 18.114Mpa.

V.RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Total deformation

Interpretation

The graph presents the total deformation in millimeters of two wall. The wall without an opening exhibits a deformation of 26.099 mm, while the wall with a circular opening shows a slightly lower deformation of 24.455 mm. This indicates that the presence of a circular opening in the wall reduces the total deformation under the specified load. This counterintuitive result may suggest that the circular opening could potentially help in redistributing the stress more evenly or that the opening configuration leads to a stiffer structural behavior in the specific context of the blast loading. Further analysis would be required to understand the underlying mechanics driving this behavior.

Equivalent Stress

Interpretation

The graph displays the equivalent stress in megapascals (MPa) for two wall. The wall without an opening experiences an equivalent stress of 116.32 MPa, whereas the wall with a circular opening shows a lower equivalent stress of 107.44 MPa. This reduction in stress for the wall with the circular opening suggests that the opening aids in distributing the load more efficiently, potentially enhancing the overall structural performance. This finding aligns with the deformation data, indicating that the circular opening may contribute to a more resilient structure under similar loading conditions, warranting further investigation into its beneficial effects.

Equivalent Elastic Strain

Interpretation

The graph provides the equivalent strain values for two wall. The wall without an opening exhibits an equivalent strain of 0.003323, while the wall with a circular opening shows a slightly lower strain of 0.00306. This indicates that the wall with the circular opening undergoes less strain compared to the wall without an opening under the same load. This reduction in strain suggests that the presence of the circular opening may improve the structural behaviour by reducing the deformation per unit length, contributing to a more efficient distribution of strain and potentially enhancing the durability and stability of the wall under high load conditions.

Shear Stress

Interpretation

The graph presents shear stress values in megapascals (MPa) for two wall. The wall without an opening experiences a shear stress of 20.039 MPa, whereas the wall with a circular opening exhibits a lower shear stress of 18.114 MPa. This reduction in shear stress for the wall with the circular opening indicates that the opening helps in mitigating shear forces, leading to a more uniform stress distribution within the wall. This result aligns with previous findings on deformation and equivalent stress, suggesting that the circular opening enhances the wall's ability to withstand applied loads more effectively by reducing peak stress concentrations.

Normal Stress

Interpretation

The graph shows normal stress values in megapascals (MPa) for two wall. The wall without an opening experiences a normal stress of 16.031 MPa, while the wall with a circular opening exhibits a lower normal stress of 14.76 MPa. This reduction in normal stress for the wall with the circular opening suggests that the opening facilitates a more even distribution of the applied load, thereby reducing the stress concentration within the wall. This finding is consistent with the observed decreases in equivalent stress, strain, and shear stress, indicating that the circular opening contributes to an overall improvement in the structural performance and load-bearing capacity of the wall.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study of precast steel fibre reinforced concrete wall-column connections with and without circular openings reveals significant findings regarding structural behavior under loading conditions. The results demonstrate that walls with circular openings exhibit lower total deformation (24.455 mm) compared to walls without openings (26.099 mm), suggesting that the presence of an opening may help redistribute stress more effectively, leading to a potentially stiffer structural response. Additionally, the equivalent stress is reduced from 116.32 MPa in solid walls to 107.44 MPa in walls with openings, indicating that the openings facilitate a more efficient load distribution and potentially enhance overall structural performance.

Further analysis of equivalent strain values supports these findings, showing a decrease from 0.003323 to 0.00306, implying improved structural behavior through reduced deformation per unit length. This reduction in strain highlights the potential for enhanced durability and stability in walls with circular openings. Moreover, shear stress analysis shows a decrease from 20.039 MPa in solid walls to 18.114 MPa in walls with openings, further indicating that the openings help mitigate shear forces and contribute to a more uniform stress distribution.

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